

Evidence of Entropy Stabilisation in Ternary Lanthanide Complexes. Lanthanide-EDTA-(O-O)Donor Ternary Complexes

S. N. LIMAYE and M. C. SAXENA*

Department of Chemistry, Dr. H. S. Gour Vishwavidyalaya, Sagar-470 003

Manuscript received 13 March 1984, revised 11 April 1985, accepted 31 July 1985

Ternary complexes of the type LN-EDTA-L have been investigated *pH*-metrically using Irving-Rossotti titration technique for the determination of formation constants. The lanthanides used are trivalent La, Ce, Pr, Nd or Sm and the (O-O) donor secondary ligands (L) are aliphatic or aromatic hydroxy acids, saturated dicarboxylic acids, unsaturated carboxylic acids, phenols or phenolic acids. The stability data have been utilised to demonstrate that these complexes are primarily entropy stabilised.

Mathematical relationships between $\log K_{ML}^M$ or $\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$ vs S_M^O (standard entropy of the metal ions) have been derived. The plots of stability constant vs S_M^O are found to be linear, suggesting that these complexes are essentially entropy stabilised. This approach is useful in view of the fact that a direct thermodynamic analysis of the ternary complexes is not possible.

CORRELATIONS between the stability constants of binary metallic complexes, and metal and ligand characteristics have been discussed in several standard texts¹⁻⁴. To the best of our knowledge there is only one reference⁵ amongst the aminopolycarboxylatolanthanide complexes attempting to show that the free energy changes in these complexes are essentially entropy changes, the conclusions being based on the fact that a linear correlation is obtained between the logarithms of the stability constant of the lanthanide-EDTA complexes and the standard entropy of the lanthanides. A direct thermodynamic analysis of the mixed-ligand complexes being not possible¹, one can assess only indirectly, about the contribution of enthalpy and/or entropy factors towards the free energy changes accompanying the formation of mixed complexes. The present communication is an attempt in this direction.

Experimental

The lanthanides on account of their large ionic radii permit complexation with coordination numbers eight or more. The ternary systems investigated are of the type LN-EDTA-L, where LN = La^{III}, Ce^{III}, Pr^{III}, Nd^{III} and Sm^{III}; EDTA = primary ligand (A); L = O-O donor secondary ligand, *viz.* aliphatic or aromatic hydroxy acid, saturated dicarboxylic acid, unsaturated carboxylic acid or phenol. The solutions of the lanthanides and EDTA were prepared as reported earlier by us⁶, and those of the secondary ligands by direct weighing and standardisation where ever necessary. All the ternary systems were studied in aqueous medium,

except in the case of salicylic, phthalic and anthranilic acids, studied in 40% (v/v) ethanol-water medium.

Usual titration sets for 1:1 binary and 1:1:1 ternary systems, in aqueous⁶ and partially aqueous⁷ media, were prepared using 1×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³ solution at an ionic strength $I=0.2$ (mol dm⁻³, NaClO₄), and titrated against 0.2 mol dm⁻³ NaOH (carbonate-free) solution at 25° using a Elico LI-120 digital *pH* meter. Reproducible *pH* readings (or corrected values⁸ in the case of partially aqueous medium) were plotted against ml of alkali added (Figs. not shown).

Results and Discussion

The practical proton-ligand stability constants ($\log K_n^H$) and metal-ligand stability constants of 1:1 binary complexes ($\log K_{ML}^M$) were evaluated using the Irving-Rossotti titration technique⁹. The extension of this technique as worked out by Chidambaram and Bhattacharya¹⁰ was used to calculate the formation constants of 1:1:1 ternary complexes ($\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$). The ternary systems under study are of the type $M+A \rightleftharpoons MA$; $MA+L \rightleftharpoons MAL$, where the secondary ligand L combines with MA forming a mixed-complex. The relative ease or difficulty experienced by the secondary ligand in the formation of mixed complex is expressed in terms of $\Delta \log K (= \log K_{MAL}^{MA} - \log K_{ML}^M)$. The ligand exchange of the type $MA+L \rightleftharpoons ML+A$, has been ignored in view of high complexing tendency and the hexadentate nature of EDTA. Also the formation of species like MA₂ and their subsequent repropportionation

into a mixed-complex as, $MA_2 + ML_2 \rightleftharpoons 2MAL$ or disproportionation of a mixed complex MAL into MA_2 and ML_2 is ruled out in view of the above fact.

A perusal of the calculated values of ΔG_{ML}^M and ΔG_{MAL}^{MA} ($\Delta G = -2.303 RT \log K$, where $\log K$ is $\log K_{ML}^M$ or $\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$), from Table 1 indicates that the numerical value of free energy change, ΔG is higher for the binary complexes than that for the ternary complexes, resulting in the stability sequence $\log K_{MAL}^{MA} < \log K_{ML}^M$. In the present case the primary ligand EDTA occupies six out of the possibly avail-

able eight coordination sites of the lanthanide metal ion. During the formation of mixed complex the incoming secondary ligand L^- or L^{2-} being negatively charged experiences an electrostatic repulsion during its combination with $(LN-EDTA)^-$. This charge repulsion lowers the stability of the mixed complex. On the other hand in case of binary complexes, the combination of L^- with LN^{3+} is favoured due to coulombic attraction. Besides this electrostatic effect, steric and the statistical considerations¹¹ are also expected to contribute to the lowering of $\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$ values as compared to $\log K_{ML}^M$. The $\Delta \log K$ values (Table 1) are consequently negative.

TABLE 1—FREE ENERGY CHANGES (kcal mol⁻¹) AND $\Delta \log K$ VALUES FOR 1:1 BINARY AND 1:1:1 TERNARY SYSTEMS

I=0.2 (mol dm⁻³ NaClO₄), temp.=25°

Ligand	ΔG and $\Delta \log K$	La ^{III}	Ce ^{III}	Pr ^{III}	Nd ^{III}	Sm ^{III}
O-O Aliphatic:						
Malic acid (ma)	$-\Delta G_{ML}^M$	5.17	5.65	5.79	6.18	6.24
	$-\Delta G_{MAL}^{MA}$	4.68	4.80	4.99	5.19	5.70
	$-\Delta \log K$	0.97	0.55	0.67	0.70	0.42
Lactic acid (la)	$-\Delta G_{ML}^M$	5.07	5.15	5.48	5.50	5.68
	$-\Delta G_{MAL}^{MA}$	4.64	4.74	4.92	5.10	5.35
	$-\Delta \log K$	0.88	0.31	0.42	0.31	0.26
Glycolic acid (ga)	$-\Delta G_{ML}^M$	4.90	5.00	5.11	5.28	5.40
	$-\Delta G_{MAL}^{MA}$	4.56	4.80	4.96	5.03	5.16
	$-\Delta \log K$	0.81	0.16	0.18	0.19	0.30
Gluconic acid (gluc)	$-\Delta G_{ML}^M$	4.08	4.35	4.49	4.68	4.88
	$-\Delta G_{MAL}^{MA}$	2.95	3.40	3.73	3.88	4.05
	$-\Delta \log K$	0.88	0.70	0.57	0.60	0.82
Malonic acid (maln)	$-\Delta G_{ML}^M$	5.24	5.60	5.87	6.20	6.71
	$-\Delta G_{MAL}^{MA}$	4.10	4.45	4.75	4.99	5.13
	$-\Delta \log K$	0.84	0.88	0.88	0.89	1.17
Succinic acid (suc)	$-\Delta G_{ML}^M$	5.14	5.32	5.66	6.02	6.19
	$-\Delta G_{MAL}^{MA}$	4.85	5.00	5.19	5.36	5.56
	$-\Delta \log K$	0.23	0.25	0.36	0.50	0.48
Glutaric acid (glut)	$-\Delta G_{ML}^M$	5.10	5.25	5.54	5.58	5.87
	$-\Delta G_{MAL}^{MA}$	3.96	4.26	4.46	4.67	4.86
	$-\Delta \log K$	0.84	0.74	0.80	0.68	0.75
Maleic acid (male)	$-\Delta G_{ML}^M$	5.76	5.99	6.55	6.96	7.16
	$-\Delta G_{MAL}^{MA}$	5.27	5.90	6.04	6.26	6.38
	$-\Delta \log K$	0.38	0.09	0.40	0.53	0.60
Citraconic acid (citra)	$-\Delta G_{ML}^M$	6.35	6.79	6.99	7.18	7.36
	$-\Delta G_{MAL}^{MA}$	5.23	5.47	5.73	5.89	6.16
	$-\Delta \log K$	0.80	0.94	0.85	0.91	0.85

(Table 1 contd.)

Itaconic acid (ita)	$-\Delta G_{ML}^M$	5.25	5.43	5.64	5.98	6.16
	$-\Delta G_{MAL}^{MA}$	4.89	5.13	5.41	5.63	5.93
	$-\Delta \log K$	0.25	0.20	0.17	0.24	0.15
Crotonic acid (crof)	$-\Delta G_{ML}^M$	4.57	4.82	5.06	5.25	5.46
	$-\Delta G_{MAL}^{MA}$	4.05	4.26	4.46	4.79	5.08
	$-\Delta \log K$	0.40	0.43	0.45	0.45	0.33
O-O Aromatic :						
Salicylic acid* (sa)	$-\Delta G_{ML}^M$	10.13	10.40	10.65	11.00	11.01
	$-\Delta G_{MAL}^{MA}$	9.73	10.08	10.34	10.45	10.63
	$-\Delta \log K$	0.24	0.20	0.19	0.20	0.24
Phthalic acid* (pha)	$-\Delta G_{ML}^M$	5.64	6.02	6.27	6.50	6.94
	$-\Delta G_{MAL}^{MA}$	4.31	4.79	5.00	5.43	5.74
	$-\Delta \log K$	1.01	0.89	0.92	0.76	0.87
Catechol (cat)	$-\Delta G_{ML}^M$	11.78	11.92	12.16	12.54	12.68
	$-\Delta G_{MAL}^{MA}$	8.85	9.01	9.29	9.70	10.88
	$-\Delta \log K$	2.85	2.15	2.20	2.10	1.75
Resorcinol (res)	$-\Delta G_{ML}^M$	6.13	6.26	6.96	7.37	8.20
	$-\Delta G_{MAL}^{MA}$	2.91	3.05	3.26	3.46	4.23
	$-\Delta \log K$	2.35	2.35	2.70	2.85	2.90
Phloroglucinol (phl)	$-\Delta G_{ML}^M$	4.82	5.17	5.37	5.54	5.79
	$-\Delta G_{MAL}^{MA}$	3.05	3.33	3.45	3.60	3.74
	$-\Delta \log K$	1.80	1.35	1.40	1.40	1.50
Protocatechuic acid (pca)	$-\Delta G_{ML}^M$	10.96	11.23	11.34	11.64	11.89
	$-\Delta G_{MAL}^{MA}$	5.85	6.15	6.38	6.76	7.03
	$-\Delta \log K$	3.75	3.71	3.63	3.78	3.58
β -Resoroylic acid (β -resa)	$-\Delta G_{ML}^M$	8.39	8.50	8.74	8.93	9.07
	$-\Delta G_{MAL}^{MA}$	5.63	5.72	5.81	6.00	6.15
	$-\Delta \log K$	2.01	2.07	2.15	2.13	2.11

* Values in partial aqueous medium ; 40% ethanol/water (v/v).

A direct thermodynamic analysis of the mixed complexes being not possible, an indirect evidence of their stabilisation by the entropy factor can be drawn from the correlation of the $\log K_{ML}^M$ and $\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$ values with the standard entropies of the metal ions. The free energy change accompanying complexation consists of the enthalpy and entropy changes. A complex may be stabilised either by the enthalpy factor or by the entropy factor, or by both. The ternary lanthanide complexes of EDTA are expected to be stabilised mainly by the entropy factor on account of two primary reasons, (i) desolvation of the acetate groups of EDTA and removal of water of hydration from metal ion¹³, and (ii) ΔH is a measure of metal-ligand bond strength; in lanthanides the 4fⁿ-electrons are well shielded from ligand perturbations due to outer

lying 5s and 5p orbitals causing the bond to be largely ionic in nature (ΔH remaining rather small). Combination of highly charged species LN^{3+} and A^{4-} in the first step and then $(LN-A)^-$ and L^{3-} (in general) in the second step, enhances the value of favourable entropy factor.

A perusal of the literature values of stability data on some binary lanthanide complexes of aminopolycarboxylic acids and other ligands supports the above arguments. Thus, for example, the ΔS and ΔH for some 1 : 1 lanthanide complexes are given in Table 2.

The mathematical relationships for the correlations between the stability constants $\log K_{ML}^M$ or $\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$ and the standard entropies (S_M^O) of the lanthanides have been derived¹³ using the relation-

TABLE 2

Ligand (Experimental conditions*) c=calorimetry	ΔS cal K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	ΔH kcal mol ⁻¹
Acetate ^a (I=2.0 M, NaClO ₄ , 25°, c)	14.6 to 19.5 La-Yb	2.18 to 8.51 (unfavourable)
Glycolate ^a (I=2.0 M, NaClO ₄ , 25°, c)	7.9 to 11.4 La-Yb	-0.63 to -0.29 (favourable but small)
Dipicolinate ^b (I=0.5 M, NaClO ₄ , 25°, c)	25.8 to 89.9 La-Lu	-3.13 to -2.19 (favourable but small)
EDTA ^c (I=0.44 M, 25°, c)	59.0 to 75.0 La-Lu	-4.1 to -3.2 (favourable but small)
dtpa ^d (I=0.1 M, KNO ₃ , 27°, c)	71.8 to 85.7 La-Lu (all favourable, large)	-5.2 to -5.1 (favourable but small)

* I. Grenthe, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1964, 18, 283. ^b I. Grenthe, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1963, 17, 2487. ^c K. B. Yatsimirskii and G. B. Prik, *Russ. J. Inorg. Chem. (Engl. Transl.)*, 1962, 7, 30; G. B. Prik, *Russ. J. Inorg. Chem. (Engl. Transl.)*, 1963, 8, 1097. ^d A. S. Carson, P. G. Lave and P. N. Smith, *J. Chem. Soc., A*, 1963, 527, 1984.

ships of the type, $\Delta G = -2.303 RT \log K$ and free energy, enthalpy and entropy changes during the formation of ML, MA and MAL. These equations under standard conditions are:

$$\log K_{ML}^M = -(2.303 R)^{-1}[S_M^O] + (2.303 R)^{-1} [S_{ML}^O - S_L^O] - (2.303 RT)^{-1} [\Delta H_{ML}^{OM}] \quad (1)$$

$$\log K_{MAL}^{MA} = -(2.303 R)^{-1}[S_M^O] + (2.303 R)^{-1} [(S_{MAL}^O - \Delta S_{MA}^{OM}) - (S_A^O + S_L^O)] - (2.303 RT)^{-1} [\Delta H_{MAL}^{OMA}] \quad (2)$$

The terms ΔH_{ML}^{OM} and ΔH_{MAL}^{OMA} represent the enthalpy changes accompanying the formation of ML and MAL, respectively, and the other terms

Fig. 1. Variation in (O) $\log K_{ML}^M$ and (Δ) $\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$ with S_M^O values of lanthanide metal ions. (L=ma, la, ga, gluc).

The plots of $\log K_{ML}^M$ or $\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$ vs S_M^O are found to be linear in the present case. Representative plots for the ternary systems [LN-EDTA-L] (L=malic, lactic, glycolic or gluconic acid) are shown in Fig. 1 and the slope values are given in Table 3. The slope values are small (~ 0.1). The linear nature of the plots justifies the validity of equations (1) and (2), and also yields an (indirect) evidence that the lanthanide complexes are predominantly entropy stabilised¹⁴. The desolvation of acetate groups of EDTA, combination of highly charged species, entropy of chelation and rupture of inner

TABLE 3—SLOPE VALUES FOR THE PLOTS OF FIG. 1

Ligand	Slope values		Ligand	Slope values		Ligand	Slope values	
	ML	MAL		ML	MAL		ML	MAL
ma	0.10	0.09	glut	0.07	0.08	pha	0.12	0.14
la	0.06	0.07	male	0.13	0.10	eat	0.08	0.16
ga	0.04	0.06	citra	0.09	0.09	res	0.20	0.12
gluc	0.08	0.10	ita	0.09	0.10	phl	0.09	0.07
maln	0.14	0.10	orot	0.08	0.09	pea	0.09	0.11
suc	0.10	0.07	sa	0.08	0.09	β -resa	0.06	0.05

have their usual meaning. It is evident from equations (1) and (2) that plots of $\log K_{ML}^M$ vs S_M^O or $\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$ vs S_M^O will be linear if the second and the third terms on the right hand side are either constant or negligible in comparison to the first term or vary linearly with first term. The plots are expected to have non-unit slopes in view of the fact that the term (S_M^O) has a coefficient $-(2.303 R)^{-1}$. Thus the entropy stabilisation of the lanthanide complexes can be demonstrated by these plots without requiring the experimental determination of ΔH and ΔS values.

hydration zones of the lanthanides¹⁵ contribute to the total entropy changes in complexation

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Prof. Y. G. Kher, Head, Department of Chemistry, for providing facilities. One of the authors (S.N.L.) is thankful to U. G. C., New Delhi, for the award of Senior Research Fellowship and the other (M.C.S.) to the M. P. Council of Science and Technology, for the award of a research grant.

References

1. F. J. C. ROSSOTTI, "Modern Coordination Chemistry", eds. J. LEWIS and R. G. WILKINS, Interscience, New York, 1960, pp. 39-67.
2. M. M. JONES, "Elementary Coordination Chemistry", Prentice-Hall, Englewood Cliffs, 1964, pp. 333-341.
3. S. CHABEREK and A. E. MARTELL, "Organic Sequestering Agents", John Wiley, New York, 1959, pp. 125-173.
4. M. T. BECK, "Chemistry of Complex Equilibria", Van Nostrand, London, 1970, pp. 240-262.
5. J. K. FOREMAN and T. D. SMITH, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 1752.
6. S. N. LIMAYE and M. C. SAXENA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1982, **59**, 698.
7. S. N. LIMAYE and M. C. SAXENA, *Nat. Acad. Sci. Lett.*, 1984, **7**, 121; *Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci., India, Sect. A*, 1984, **54**, 109.
8. VAN UITERT, L. G. HAAS and O. G. FERRELIUS, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, **75**, 451, 455.
9. H. M. IRVING and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 3397; 1954, 2904.
10. M. V. CHIDAMBARAM and P. K. BHATTACHARYA, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1970, **32**, 3271.
11. P. K. BHATTACHARYA, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1981, **40**, 382.
12. S. J. ASHCROFT and C. T. MORTIMER, "Thermochemistry of Transition Metal Complexes", Academic Press, London, 1970, pp. 130, 406.
13. S. N. LIMAYE, Ph. D. Thesis, Dr. H. S. Gour Vishwavidyalaya, 1983.
14. S. N. LIMAYE and M. C. SAXENA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1984, **61**, 748.